

Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) Template: Version 1.0

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What is this template:

The attached template is intended to facilitate the process of documenting a standard operating procedure (SOP) within the context of an academic research effort. This template was developed for research teams to use within and/or across different research projects but may be useful in other contexts.

Broadly, an SOP is simply a set of step-by-step instructions for performing a routine activity. Documenting these instructions, rather than having undocumented “ways of doing things” helps with the following:

1. Communication and expectation setting
2. Onboarding and training (e.g. of new team members)
3. Ensuring that research-related practices and strategies are applied in a consistent and standardized manner.
4. Ensuring that research-related practices and strategies are applied safely and in compliance with appropriate regulations and policies (e.g. HIPAA).
5. Efficiency and quality control within research workflows

How to use this template:

Standard Operating Procedures are a form of research-related documentation. A good rule of thumb in this context is to document more than you think is necessary and in greater specificity than you think might be necessary.

The best way for teams or individuals to use this template is use it as a starting point for systematizing their routine practices. The goal is not to be evaluative. The template uses the brewing of coffee as an illustrative example and there are many, many ways to brew a worthwhile cup of coffee. This is just a format for getting started.

An SOP can cover even the most “mundane” of activities, including setting standards for how project-related files should be named and organized. The SOP should reflect current practice, if a particular step needs to be changed for some reason, that should be reflected in the documentation and communicated to any team members affected.

SOPs can certainly be developed collaboratively, but it is often helpful to designate an individual or small group of individuals who are on point for answering questions, updating the documentation as necessary, and ensuring that any related activities are being implemented as described.

Within the template: Text in italics is meant as an example. Plain red text is used to describe the contents of each section. All the text can be deleted as the template is applied.

TITLE: <i>Coffee Protocol</i>	
VERSION: 2	PREVIOUS VERSION: https://doi.org/10.17504/protocols.io.bw7yphpw
LAST UPDATED: <i>September 23, 2024</i>	
SOP MAINTAINED BY: <i>John Borghi</i>	

IMPLEMENTATION CHECKED BY: <i>John Borghi</i>	FREQUENCY: <i>Continuously</i>
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1. PURPOSE

The purpose of this SOP is to standardize the process of brewing a pot of coffee using a standard drip coffee machine and a few fussy accessories.

This section outlines the goal of the SOP and describes why the SOP is in place. It can be as simple as wanting (or needing) to standardize a set of processes.

2. PERSONNEL

This SOP applies to every member of the research team, including students, postdocs, professional staff, and the PI.

This section describes to whom the SOP applies and who is responsible for ensuring that it is implemented properly. SOPs can apply to everyone within a research group, everyone within a broader collaboration, or whatever group makes sense given the activities described in the SOP.

3. RELATED EXPECTATIONS

It is expected that the research team member who finishes a batch of coffee will prepare a new batch in accordance with the steps outlined in this SOP.

The SOP maintainer (John) will supply all of the ingredients (plus milk and sugar) and ensure that the coffee pot is cleaned by the end of the work day, but individual lab members are responsible for cleaning their own mugs.

This section outlines any expectations related to SOP. This may include the scope of the SOP (i.e. how broadly it should apply), the frequency by which it should be applied, etc.

4. STEP-BY-STEP INSTRUCTIONS

Finally! This is the part of the SOP where the step-by-step instructions for the activity are documented in detail. Remember, it is typically better to document more than you think is

necessary and in greater specificity than you think might be necessary. The goal should be to leave as little room for alternative interpretations as possible.

These instructions use a 1:17 ratio for drip coffee. This is roughly 4 ounces of water for every tablespoon of ground coffee.

1. Remove used filter/coffee grounds from the machine and rinse out the pot.
2. Measure out exactly 30 grams of coffee beans using the kitchen scale located in the cabinet under the coffee machine. Do not use lab equipment for making coffee please.
3. Grind coffee to a fine grind (about 30 seconds)
4. Place coffee filter in the basket of the machine and then add ground coffee, spreading evenly.
5. Add exactly 510 grams of filtered water to the machine.
6. Press the power button on the machine.
7. While coffee is brewing, refill the water pitcher and place it back in the refrigerator.

5. NOTES, LINKS, & RESOURCES

Coffee beans, grinder, and kitchen scale are all located in the cabinet under the coffee machine in the break room. Please do not use lab equipment when making coffee.

Filtered water can be found in the pitcher in the refrigerator. Please refill the pitcher after use. Sugar and oat milk can be found in the cabinet and refrigerator respectively.

There are plenty of tea options available as well, but that's a different SOP.

This section provides extra context to the SOP. This is where any applicable training materials, tips, and other information can be referenced.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Acknowledged By:	Date
John Borghi	September 23, 2024

This optional section can be added to keep track of who has reviewed the SOP and when they last reviewed it.